

Motives and attitudes in choosing the nursing profession among students at Medical University – Sofia

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Abstract

Choosing the nursing profession is a complex process in which individual motivational factors intersect with societal needs, particularly in the context of increasing demands on nursing staff and a chronic shortage of healthcare professionals.

This study aims to analyze the motives and attitudes influencing the choice of the nursing profession among students at the Medical University of Sofia. The empirical study was conducted between September and November 2025 and included 174 nursing students from all years of study.

The results highlight the predominance of value-based and humane motives in professional choice and emphasize the need for targeted policies for career guidance and the sustainable development of nursing staff within the healthcare system.

Keywords

Attitudes, motives, nurse, professional development, students

Introduction

Issues related to occupational choice have attracted scholarly attention since antiquity, including the works of ancient Greek philosophers such as Socrates and Plato and the French thinkers Pascal, Voltaire, and Rousseau. They have been the subject of attention of representatives of a variety of philosophical, educational, economic, and other schools and teachings, from the humanism of the Renaissance to rationalism in the era of the initial accumulation of capital (Vodenitcharov 1986, 1992; Kirkov 2025).

The choice of a professional path is a multilayered process in which personal attitudes and social needs intersect. In this context, the operating mechanisms for managing and regulating the reproduction of labor potential are tested precisely through decisions related to profession-

al orientation. The educational system, the processes of professional guidance and selection, and the mechanisms for qualification and retraining of the workforce play a significant role in the formation of this choice. In view of the growing demands of modern society, as well as the dynamic social and scientific and technical development, it can be expected that in the future the processes of professional self-determination and development of young people will be faced with even higher and more complex requirements (Kirkov 2024, 2025).

The nursing profession is a central part of the modern health system, playing a key role in the organization and delivery of health care. Health care, as a set of diagnostic, curative, preventive, promotional, rehabilitative, and other activities, requires complex interaction between different professional groups, with nurses standing di-

rectly next to the patient at every stage of care. The historical context of the development of nursing traces the transformation from the religious and charitable care of the 19th century to the modern goals of the profession, based on scientific principles and standardized practices (Baly 1995; McCrae 2003).

The profession officially emerged in the 19th century with the creation of the first systematized nursing curricula, most famously in the person of Florence Nightingale, who laid the foundations of modern nursing by emphasizing hygiene, professional training, and health statistics. Over time, nursing has evolved from a role as an adjunct to medical practice to an autonomous profession with its standards of training, ethics, and professional regulation. This development is also reflected in concepts of division of labor in health care, which delineate clear boundaries and competencies between physicians, nurses, pharmacists, and other professionals to maximize the effectiveness of patient care (Straus et al. 1963; Hall 2005).

The choice of the profession of „nursing“ is a complex and multifactorial process that cannot be explained solely by rational economic reasons. The leading motives that determine the decision to choose and apply for the specialty of „nursing“ can be conditionally divided into two main groups. The first group includes humane motives related to the desire to provide care for sick people, support the healing process, and actively participate in the protection and improvement of public health. The nursing profession is perceived as a socially significant, humane, and morally engaging activity aimed at supporting the patient and the patient's relatives. The second group of motives is related to personal fulfillment and professional development and includes the pursuit of secure professional fulfillment, employment opportunities in the country and abroad, relative financial stability, professional independence, and the opportunity to fully apply and develop personal abilities and skills within the health system. The shortage of nurses in many countries has further stimulated the interest of academic researchers in the motivational aspects behind the choice of profession, which are often related to working conditions, opportunities for professional development, and social recognition (Mudallal et al. 2017).

The purpose of this article is to present and analyze the motives and attitudes toward choosing the profession of „nursing“ among students of this specialty from all courses of study at the Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tsekomir Vodenitcharov, MD, DSc“ of the Medical University – Sofia. The study is based on a combination of empirical data and a theoretical overview.

Materials and methodology of the research

The subject of the study is students in the specialty „nursing“ at the Medical University – Sofia.

The study was conducted during the period September 2025–November 2025 in the city of Sofia, and 174 students studying in the specialty of nursing participated.

The study used a wide range of sociological and statistical methods: documentary method, survey method—nursing students from MU-Sofia were surveyed with an independently developed questionnaire, descriptive analysis, analysis of variance, Pearson χ^2 test, and graphical analysis to visualize the results obtained. The indicators were assessed at a significance level $\alpha = 0.05$.

Quantitative analyses were performed using the statistical software package SPSS 17.0. Microsoft Office products were used for tabular and graphical processing and presentation.

Results and discussion

In the context of growing public expectations for the professional and personal qualities of nurses, the need for a thorough analysis of the processes of professional orientation to the specialty „nursing“ and the formation of nursing staff in higher medical schools is becoming increasingly relevant. The concept of higher medical education and the lack of gender-based selection mechanisms for candidate students in the specialty „nursing“ have an impact on the formation of their sociodemographic profile. The present study covers 174 students from all courses of study in the specialty of nursing, of whom 4.60% are men and 95.40% are women. The lack of a quota principle in training in the specialty of nursing is the reason that over 90% of the trained and subsequently working nurses are female. Gender-balanced teams have better dynamics, psychological, and emotional stability, which in training and implementation in this specialty could be achieved by introducing a quota principle, just as in the 1960s the quota principle was introduced for the admission of students in the specialties of „medicine,“ „dental medicine,“ and „pharmacy“ to ensure equal gender representation. Excessive feminization in nursing care can cause problems with the provision of human resources in areas of health care requiring endurance and technical skills.

The results in Fig. 1 show that the majority of respondents (94%) applied once, which indicates a clear and pur-

Figure 1. How many times have you applied for the specialty „nursing“?

purposeful choice of the profession from the first application. This high proportion suggests a clear awareness of the content of the training and the professional responsibilities associated with nursing. The small share of respondents (6%) who applied twice can be interpreted as an indicator of sustainability and constancy in professional intentions. Reapplication in this group is determined by external factors such as limited admission or competition and not by hesitation in choosing the specialty. The presence of such a share of respondents complements the profile of the nurse as a profession, which for some of the trainees represents a long-term goal requiring targeted efforts. In summary, the results indicate that the choice of the specialty „nursing“ in the studied cohort is mostly conscious and motivated, which is an important prerequisite for professional commitment, satisfaction with training, and future sustainability in the practice of the profession.

The choice of profession and specialty is a significant life decision that predetermines the professional and social development of individuals in their life path. It is important to pay attention to the motives for choosing a specialty.

To analyze these questions, the respondents were asked when they decided to choose the specialty „nursing,“ who influenced them in choosing this specialty, and whether they have a close relative with a medical profession (Figs 2, 3, 4).

The smallest share (7%) of individuals made the decision to choose the profession of „nursing“ before completing secondary education. Although limited in number, this group reflects the presence of a strong early identification with the profession, often determined by value attitudes, family tradition, or an expressed desire to work in the field of care and assistance for others.

The distribution of responses shows that the choice of the nursing profession is most often formed at a later stage of educational development, while at the same time, there is a significant group of respondents with earlier conscious professional motivation. This emphasizes the importance of career guidance and information about the profession of „nursing“ both in secondary education and immediately after its completion.

The results in Fig. 2 show that for the majority of respondents (74%) the decision to choose a profession was made after completing secondary education. This high relative share suggests that for the majority of the par-

Figure 2. When did you decide to choose the nursing profession?

ticipants in the study, the choice was the result of a more mature and thoughtful process, influenced by a realistic assessment of the opportunities for professional realization, as well as by information about the specifics of the nursing profession.

Almost one-fifth of the respondents (19%) indicated that they made the decision during their secondary education. This indicates an earlier formation of a professional orientation, which may be related to an interest in medical specialties, the influence of the educational environment, or contact with the health system through the family or personal experience. This group of respondents probably developed a purposeful motivation at an early age, which facilitates the subsequent choice of professional training.

Figure 3. Who influenced you to choose the nursing profession?

The results presented in Figs 3 and 4 allow for a deeper understanding of the role of personal motivation and the social environment in the formation of professional choice. The data show that for the majority of respondents (76%) the choice of specialty is the result of a personal decision, which emphasizes the autonomous nature of motivation and the presence of a conscious desire for professional realization in nursing. This result is indicative of a high degree of internal motivation, which is a key factor for sustainability and long-term commitment to the profession.

In addition, the influence of the social environment cannot be ignored. Although representing a smaller relative share, some of the respondents indicate parents (8%), friends (7%), or a nurse (9%) as the main factor that influenced their choice. These results show that direct or indirect acquaintance with the profession through close or professional models plays a significant role in forming a positive attitude toward nursing, especially when it is presented through personal example and real professional experience.

The data in Fig. 4 complement this interpretation, with almost half of the respondents (47%) indicating that they have a close person employed in the medical profession, while a slightly larger share (53%) lacks such a connection. The support and influence of parents and relatives in choosing a professional path is a long and multilayered process that can be realized both through targeted and conscious influences and through spontaneous and informal interactions. The family environment, established professional traditions, and communication in the home

environment contribute to the formation of shared attitudes and a kind of “collective” decision when choosing the specialty “nurse.” On the other hand, this distribution shows that although the family environment has an influence on professional orientation, the choice of the profession is not necessarily determined by family tradition. On the contrary, the significant share of respondents without relatives in the medical field who nevertheless chose this profession confirms the leading role of personal motivation and individual value attitudes.

Figure 4. Do you have a close relative (mother, father, siblings, and other close family members) in the medical profession?

Respondents were also asked what the main motives were when choosing the nursing specialty (Fig. 5). The results clearly outline the dominant role of value-oriented motives in choosing the profession. The overwhelming majority of respondents (87.3% or 152 participants) define nursing as a humane and noble profession, which emphasizes the desire to help and care for others as the main driving factor for professional choice. This result confirms the social mission of nursing and corresponds to the ideas established in the scientific literature about the profession as a vocation requiring a high degree of empathy and moral commitment.

A significantly smaller proportion of respondents indicated pragmatic motives, such as financial stability (6.9% or 12 participants) and the prestige of the profession (5.8% or 10 participants). This distribution shows that economic and socio-status factors are of secondary importance in the choice of the specialty in the studied co-

Figure 5. What are your main reasons for choosing the specialty “nursing”?

hort. Although less pronounced, these motives should not be underestimated, as they can have an impact on long-term professional satisfaction and retention of personnel in the health care system. The results indicate that the choice of the specialty „nursing“ is predominantly based on internal, value-oriented motivation, while external incentives related to financial and status considerations have a complementary role. This structure of motivation is an important prerequisite for professional dedication and sustainability but at the same time emphasizes the need to improve working conditions to support and preserve this strong internal motive.

Inferences and conclusion

The results of the empirical study show that the choice of the profession „nurse“ among students from the Medical University – Sofia is characterized by a high degree of awareness and predominant autonomy in decision-making. The majority of students choose the specialty after completing their secondary education, which confirms that professional self-determination in this area is the result of a long process of reflection and assessment of personal priorities and future professional prospects. The analysis of the sociodemographic profile reveals a clearly expressed feminization of the specialty. The family environment emerges as a significant, albeit mostly indirect, factor of influence, in which professional traditions and daily communication contribute to the formation of attitudes by students as a personal choice. The leading motive for choosing the profession remains the humane and socially significant nature of nursing activity, complemented by a desire for professional fulfillment, prestige, and relative financial stability.

The nursing profession continues to be perceived by students as morally significant, socially necessary, and professionally promising, despite the challenges facing the modern health care system. The results obtained confirm that the motivation for choosing this profession is formed at the intersection of humane values and pragmatic considerations related to professional realization and employment security. In this context, the role of higher medical education and the process of professional orientation is key to attracting and retaining young people in the nursing profession. The need for targeted educational and health policies aimed at improving the public image, working conditions, and development opportunities of nurses is essential for the sustainable development of human resources in health care. The analysis of the results of the study outlines the profile of the future nurse as a person with clearly expressed internal motivation, strong humane values, and a conscious professional choice. Understanding these motivational factors is essential for developing effective strategies for attracting and retaining nursing staff, as well as for the sustainable development of the nursing profession in the face of growing health care needs.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.